

NOIRLab Library Services

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NOIRLab's Library Services is a service within Research and Science Services (RSS) that serves all NOIRLab staff. We support the mission and scientific activities of NOIRLab by providing a variety of services. We also collaborate with other observatory librarians to share expertise and to offer collective support to the user community.

The NOIRLab Library Services maintains three physical locations with collections of journals, books, and historical materials: Tucson, Arizona; Hilo, Hawai'i; and La Serena, Chile. We maintain institutional subscriptions to print and

electronic journals and purchase books and ebooks on request. To aid in research endeavors, Library Services staff provide assistance in locating and obtaining journal articles, books, and other materials; developing citation lists; and filling information requests.

Following are details on several of the key services provided by the NOIRLab Library Services.

Publications Tracking: Citation analysis and bibliometrics are important tools for measuring the scientific productivity

Figure 1. Tucson Headquarters Library Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA. R.T. Sparks

and impact of observatories as well as the return on investment of public and private funds used in advancing astronomical research. One of the main functions of the NOIRLab Library Services is to track publications written by NOIRLab staff and all community publications that make use of our telescopes, data products, and services. We maintain two ADS public libraries: the [NOIRLab ADS bibliographic group](#) for refereed NOIRLab telescope publications and the [NOIRLab Staff Publications ADS public library](#) for refereed and non-refereed staff publications. The metrics derived from publication tracking are used in NOIRLab reports and proposals. To ensure that NOIRLab is appropriately recognized in scientific publications, we maintain the [AAS Facility Keywords](#) for NOIRLab and the [NOIRLab Scientific Acknowledgments](#) web page.

Page Charges: Library Services oversees the processing of page charge requisitions for the NOIRLab author portion of publications.

Website: Library Services maintains web pages both on the intranet website for the use of our staff and on the [science website](#).

Archival Materials: Library Services helps to preserve the history of the organization through its archival collections. We preserve, organize, and provide access to this historical material to NOIRLab staff as well as to individuals outside the organization. The Tucson Headquarters Library has a rich collection of historical materials: books, documents, correspondence, images, and glass plates.

Figure 2. **(right)** Library facilities in Hilo Credit: *International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Pollard*
(inset above) Library facilities in Chile Credit: *NOIRLab/NSF/AURA*

